

ISic0021

I.Sicily inscription 0021

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Imp(eratori) · Caes(ari) · divi
2. Magni · Antoni
3. ni f(ilio) divi · Septimi
4. Severi n(epoti) M(arco) Aure
5. lio Severo A
6. lexandro Pio Fel(ici)
7. Aug(usto) · pont(ifici) · max(imo) · tri(bunicia)
8. pot(estate) [] co(n)s(uli) p(atri) p(atriciae) co[l](onia)
9. Aug(usta) · Panh[or]m(itanorum)
10. d(ecurionum) d(ecreto)

Apparatus

Text of

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491781

EDR 137778

EDCS 22000865

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7279 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650789>)

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Wilson, R.J.A. 1990. Sicily under the Roman Empire: the archaeology of a Roman province, 36 B.C. - A.D. 535. Warminster. At 358 n.40

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